

Asthma Is Curable via Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door

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Abstract

Asthma is a chronic condition that affects the airways in the lungs. Patients' airways can become inflamed and narrowed, making it difficult for air to flow normally. The exact causes of asthma are unknown, and there is currently no cure for the condition. Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu suggests that if a medical condition is resistant to conventional treatment, it may be a karmic disease, encompassing spiritual ailments as well. Within the realm of Dharma, such karmic diseases can often be successfully addressed and even fully resolved. In Master Lu's totem reading program conducted over the telephone, it is asserted that the root cause of asthma lies in the presence of spirits within the affected individuals. To validate the authenticity of Master Lu's teachings, we examined five severe cases of asthma, exploring the impact of the practice of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door on their well-being. Remarkably, all five patients experienced a complete cure for their asthma. These results further support Master Lu's theory: if a disease is incurable by conventional medical means, it is a karmic and/or spiritual illness, which is treatable through Dharma practice.

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Introduction

Asthma, a common chronic respiratory disease, affects >200 million people worldwide and causes about 450,000 deaths each year [1]. About 1 in 13 people in the USA has asthma. It affects people of all ages and often starts during childhood. Certain things can set off or worsen asthma symptoms, such as pollen, exercise, viral infections, or cold air. These are called asthma triggers. When symptoms get worse, it is called an asthma attack, flare-up [2], or exacerbation.

Severe asthma is associated with an increased risk for exacerbations, reduced lung function, fixed airflow obstruction, and substantial morbidity and mortality [3]. Severe asthma is also associated with high healthcare utilization [4]. Epidemiological studies showed that the mortality rate of asthma in children is still high worldwide [5]. While both the incidence and mortality rates have shown a decline, older individuals with asthma exhibit not just more severe symptoms but also demonstrate an elevated mortality rate [6]. Asthma control is therefore essential to minimize its exacerbations, which can be fatal if the condition is poorly controlled [5].

Asthma is characterized in the majority by type 2 airway inflammation. Type 2 inflammation results in the secretion of interleukin-4, -5 and -13 in the airways and the recruitment of inflammatory cells [7]. Initially considered an allergic disorder driven by mast cells and eosinophils, asthma is now recognized as a complex syndrome with various clinical phenotypes and immunological endotypes [8].

People with asthma are burdened by breathlessness, cough and other disabling symptoms resulting in impaired quality of life [9]. Even worse, the co-occurrence of asthma and overweight is becoming an increasingly common health problem. More than half of the subjects with severe or difficult-to-treat asthma are overweight. Currently, there are no specific guidelines for the treatment of this group of patients [10].

It can be predicted that asthma will remain a health challenge in the future for a long time. If there is a method that can cure it, it will be desirable for human well-being.

Dharma offers a precise explanation of the causes of asthma and its treatment methods. To illustrate the causes, we present three dialogues in which Master Lu addresses questions from asthma patients, pointing out the cause and effect of their condition. For

the treatment approach, we provide five cases that demonstrate how practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door can cure asthma.

Etiology

Asthma is one of the most common chronic conditions affecting people of various age groups, yet much remains to be learned of its etiology [11]. The most updated National Institutes of Health (NIH) website states that “the exact causes for developing asthma are unknown [2]”, but lists 9 risk factors: Things in the environment (called allergens), viral infections, family history, allergies, obesity, race or ethnicity, sex, occupational hazards, and climate change. Based on current scientific knowledge, there is no cure for asthma. These statements objectively reflect the scientific community's understanding of asthma, emphasizing that its causes are still unknown.

When science reaches its bottleneck, exploring other perspectives may reveal the answer. Next, let's examine the causes of asthma from the perspective of Dharma. The following are three phone dialogues in which listeners ask Master Lu about the causes of asthma in the Buddhist Question and Answer (Q&A) programs, specifically “Wenda” and “Zongshu”.

Q&A 1: Asthma is a karmic disease [12]

Listener: My daughter is 11 years old and has asthma. This is usually a karmic disease, right?

Master: Yes, it is a karmic disease.

Listener: Approximately how many Little Houses are needed for her karmic creditors?

Master: Keep reciting them for her, in batches of 21. You can burn two or three each day. It takes time to accumulate enough to see improvement.

Listener: She has already improved a lot because I helped her perform life liberation and made vows. She only has occasional mild asthma now.

Master: That's not a problem.

Q&A 2: An asthma patient has many spirits in her throat (excerpt) [13]

Listener: Please help me look at a woman born in 1970, the Year of the Dog, and check her gynecological and asthma conditions.

Master: She has many spirits in her throat area.

Listener: How many Little Houses does she need? What about her karmic obstacles?

Master: No wonder, her asthma is related to two places: her lungs and her heart. Not only are her lungs unhealthy, but her heart also has problems; it is very weak. She feels exhausted all over and sleeps poorly.

Listener: Yes, that's correct.

Master: Her gynecological issues are mainly in her uterus.

Listener: Yes, she had a tumor there.

Master: She has had growths there. She should be cautious now

and stop eating meat, especially live animals.

Q&A 3: Ancestors' killing karma resulted in descendant's asthma (excerpt) [14]

Listener: I had asthma when I was 3, and now I still have it.

Master: Let me look a spirit is in your body. You wait a moment. I'll see who it is.

Listener: I rely on drugs to control my symptoms.

Master: Oops, there are 2 animals' spirits in your body. One is like a wolf. The other has eyes like Mickey Mouse. Have you ever put any Mickey Mouse in your house in the past? Have you ever put any animals in your house? Have you ever had any taxidermy animals?

Listener: I'm not sure, because I'm also.

Master: I mean your parents' home.

Listener: No taxidermy was ever put in their house.

Master: Ever? And did your dad ever kill animals? Big animals, for example.

Listener: My dad did. He killed animals because my dad is a chicken farmer.

Master: Well.

Listener: Yes. As a result, that is my ancestor's karma of killing.

Master: Ancestral karma of killing. You are a kind person, but you were born into this family to receive karmic retribution from your dad. Don't you understand?

Listener: Yes. Asthma has bothered me for >20 years and I haven't recovered yet.

Master: Do you know why? First, you suffer retribution instead of your father, which makes your father sad; second, your father's friend helped your father specialize in this kind of killing business. That guy passed away early. His soul (spirit) entered your body.

Listener: Yes, that is my third uncle. He worked with my dad and then died in a car accident.

Master: See? Now I'm telling you that's it!

Listener: yes, yes, yes. He also loved me a lot when he was alive.

Master: Trouble. His soul (spirit) is in your body.

Listener: Yeah. My right arm doesn't work well like it's pulled by a spirit or something else.

Master: That's him!

These three dialogues suggest that, according to Master Lu's teachings, asthma is attributed to karma, with spirits manifesting in the body, particularly in the respiratory system. His philosophy for healing asthma involves removing karma and helping these spirits ascend from the body through Dharma practice. Once the karma is removed and the spirits have departed, patients are expected to recover naturally. Since the spiritual world is beyond the observation of ordinary people, the true cause of asthma has remained undetected for centuries.

Results

Case 1: The boundless power of Dharma cured my asthma

I am a Dharma practitioner from Zhejiang Province, China. Before studying Buddhism, I was plagued with various illnesses: severe asthma, heart disease, lumbar spine disease, cervical spondylosis, muscle aches throughout my body, and stiffness in my hands and feet. In May 2018, I formally began practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door under the guidance of Master Jun Hong Lu, a world-renowned Buddhist master. By consistently listening to recordings of Master Lu's Dharma Conferences and His Zongshu (Buddhist Q&A of totem reading) programs, I gradually came to understand that all these ailments were the result of negative karma accumulated in my past and present lives.

In my childhood, ignorant of Buddhist teachings, I committed acts of killing: I would catch frogs, smash them, and feed them to our family's ducks, and I even boiled ants alive. In my youth, I went fishing. After moving to Ningbo City, I developed a taste for live sea animals, such as shrimp, shellfish, and live crabs. Master Lu once enlightened us that steaming a crab to death equates to the karmic burden of killing 100 fish.

I also had an abortion. I remember developing severe asthma in the winter of the year I had the abortion. The child's soul had nowhere to go and was attached to my body, resulting in my illness. For 20 to 30 years, I often struggled to breathe and relied on steroid inhalers and asthma medication to sustain my life. After understanding the cause, I began to practice the Three Golden Buddhist Practices (also known as Three Great Dharma Gems)—making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation—to pray to the Bodhisattva to heal my spiritual illness.

Every day, besides completing my daily recitation of Buddhist scriptures, I recited Little Houses. In June 2019, I vowed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva:

- Be a lifelong vegetarian;
- Not kill sentient beings;
- Release 10,000 fish gradually.

After reciting >60 Little Houses for the aborted child, my asthma unknowingly healed. I realized that the aborted child had been ascended.

Over the past five years, I have recited nearly 800 Little Houses for my karmic creditors and over 100 Little Houses for deceased souls. My heart disease, lumbar spine disease, cervical spondylosis, muscle aches, and stiffness in my limbs have all been cured. I am deeply grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva for mercifully saving me.

Dharma practitioner: H29.

Comments:

- "When we are born into this world, ignorance always follows us, causing us to make many mistakes because we do not understand the truth of the world. This is why we suffer;

we understand nothing and are unwilling to ask others [15]." If she had known that killing and abortion would cause asthma, she wouldn't have done it. Ignorance is very frightening because it leads us to create negative karma without realizing it.

Case 2: Practices of Dharma has finally eradicated my 20-year asthma

I got asthma in 2007 when I was 45 years old. Every night at 2 o'clock I began to cough, spit, and chest tightness. I could not come up for air, could not lie down, could only curl up on the sofa coughing, wheezing, very suffocating, snot and tears, basically all night sitting up until dawn.

Since then, I have been on a relentless journey seeking medical treatment. I have tried Chinese medicine, Western medicine, major hospitals, and street clinics—anywhere I heard of a doctor who could cure asthma, I went. I took medicine daily and frequently received infusions, leaving my hands full of needle marks. However, the treatments only controlled the symptoms temporarily, and I continued to wheeze and struggle to breathe at night.

My asthma has been lingering for many years, like an unyielding disease that refuses to go away.

In 2013, I began exploring Dharma online and made offerings to the Three Saints of the Western Pure Land of Ultimate Bliss. At that time, I believed in Buddhism but did not practice it. I was foolish and ignorant, unaware of the principles of cause and effect. I disliked everything I saw, frequently lost my temper, and felt low every day. I constantly felt like a failure, and life was painful.

I am grateful to the heavens for their mercy and to the Buddhas and Bodhisattvas for their compassion. In 2017, I was fortunate to discover Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. Watching Master Lu's enlightening videos, including his Totem readings and his Dharma teachings, I felt like a lost child finding their way home. I saw hope. I finally realized that asthma is a spiritual illness and understood that I needed to ascend the spirits in my body to cure my asthma.

I began to follow Master Lu's teachings, practicing the Three Golden Buddhist Practices of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door: making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation. I consistently did daily recitations, reciting Little House in batches of 21 to ascend my karmic creditors and the miscarried child, and to resolve karmic conflicts.

Soon, I made significant vows to Guan Yin Bodhisattva:

- Become a lifelong vegetarian;
- Live an ascetic life;
- Respect my master and His teachings;
- Attain enlightenment in one lifetime.

I diligently recited Little House to eliminate karma and repay karmic debts, managing to recite 5-7 Little Houses a day.

Little House proved to be incredibly efficacious! From the first

day I started reciting Buddhist scriptures, I stopped needing fluids. Each day, my condition improved, allowing me to reduce my medication dose. By following Master Lu's Dharma teachings, observing precepts, and cultivating my mind, I began sleeping well at night. My condition improved significantly, bringing immense Dharma joy!

Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu saved both my physical and spiritual life, transforming my entire existence. Once, I was a foolish sentient being lost in the Saha world, with the branch of my life withering away. Master Lu compassionately helped me attach the willow branch of the Guan Yin Bodhisattva, revitalizing my withered branch and allowing it to flourish! Master Lu taught me the truth of being human and the meaning of compassion for all sentient beings.

Through Little House, I was able to ascend my deceased ancestors, karmic creditors, and other invisible beings, leading to my gradual recovery. My sickly body is now gone, replaced by a strong and healthy one. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door has cured my stubborn asthma, freeing me from pain and helping me through difficult times. I extend infinite gratitude to Namó Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva and to Master Lu for blessing me in my dreams!

Buddhist practitioner: Z30.

Comments:

- Unborn children, whether lost through intentional abortion or unintentional miscarriage, create profound karmic obstacles. Although they have not come into the world, they are still considered human beings, and the karma of taking a human life is severe. Abortion means that the family does not accept the child, but since the child's inherent lifespan has not ended, the underworld does not accept them either. As a result, they become wandering, orphaned spirits. It is only after several decades, when the child's lifespan naturally ends, that they can reincarnate. Therefore, terminating an embryo's life leaves the infant's spirit with no place to belong, plunging them into a tragic situation. By reciting Buddhist scriptures for them and helping them ascend, it is as if they gain merits and virtues, allowing them to reincarnate earlier [16].
- These unfortunate spirits, with nowhere to go and a life owed by their mother, often attached to their mother's body, causing harm. They may also attach to their mother's other children, leading to conditions such as autism or rebellious behavior. Causing asthma is one form of retaliation.

Case 3: My 43-year allergic bronchial asthma was healed by practicing Dharma

I am from Shandong Province, China.

I have very serious allergic bronchial asthma (ABA). I have wheezed very badly since I was a child. When I am sick, I can't move around, and I can't catch my breath. My lips are purple, and I even have shit in my pants, which is painful! I have suffered from ABA for 43 years.

I came into contact with Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door in 2012 through my good friend, Dharma practitioner Sun. Sun offered me a book by Master Lu and a CD-ROM of Master Lu's Totem reading. Practitioner Sun said that Master Lu has a Dharma eye and reads totems and diagnoses illnesses. It was amazing! At that time, I thought, "Is there anything in the world that is so magical?" After practitioner Sun left, I couldn't wait to put the CD-ROM on my computer and watch the video. The video of Master Lu interpreting totems was really amazing! I didn't even eat at noon that day, and I watched it until the evening. I thought it would be great if Master Lu could read my totem so that I could breathe smoothly. I made up my mind that I would also recite Buddhist scriptures to ascend my karmic creditors.

A few days later, practitioner Sun introduced me to a senior practitioner who lives in the same community where I reside. He taught me how to practice the Three Golden Buddhist Practices. He taught me how to pray, recite Buddhist scriptures, make a vow, and release living creatures. On the first day, I began reciting Buddhist scriptures, my daily recitation was set at >21 times per day for each scripture, except for the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*. I wanted to recite more, so I could familiarize myself with Buddhist scriptures faster. I memorized the *Heart Sutra*, *Cundi Dharani*, *Xiao Zai Ji Xiang Shen Zhou* and other short Buddhist scriptures very quickly. The *Great Compassion Mantra* took me one month to memorize. I spent all my time reciting Buddhist scriptures every day except for eating and sleeping.

After a week of reciting Buddhist scriptures, I wanted to set up a Buddhist altar at home. I inquired my husband's opinion, and he agreed readily. He thought that reciting Buddhist scriptures with him at home was better than doing nothing full of boring. So, I quickly ordered a large table and set up a Buddhist altar in a special room.

ABA is a condition often likened to an incurable cancer, and those who suffer from it live in a state of constant torment! When it attacked me in 2000, my husband took me to a big Hospital to see a doctor. At that time, the hospital could only check for 30 allergens. I was allergic to them all! The doctors were stunned. They said that I had >30 allergies and that it was the first time they had ever seen a patient with such a serious condition as mine.

Healthy people do not know how painful this disease is. In those years, I had to take medication and injections every day, and I had to carry first-aid sprays with me when I stepped out. Once I was sick, luckily my home was close to the hospital. I got a doctor in my village to give me a shot of adrenal sebaceous hormone and then called 120 for an emergency. It was already blue on my face, purple on my lips, and soft on my body.

Since the first day I met Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, my daily recitation has not been interrupted for a day. I repaid my karmic creditors with many Little Houses, 21 sheets per set. To save time, I cooked one dish at a time for two meals. I even saved drinking water time for recitation. I could recite 12 Little Houses in a day. As a result, I feel that my breathing is becoming smoother over time.

On March 18, 2013, I had the honor of becoming a disciple of

Master Lu in Malaysia. When I paid my respects to Master Lu, He blessed me for a long, long time. The compassionate look in His eyes is still imprinted in my mind. At that time, I (soul) flew up to the sky and saw two very tall, armor-clad, sword-wielding Dharma Protectors standing on both sides of the South Heavenly Gate. The scene in the sky was so beautiful that I didn't want to come down.

After I came back from the worshiping ceremony, I made vows to Guan Yin Bodhisattva:

- Be a vegetarian for the rest of my life;
- Not kill sentient beings, not eat live sea animals;
- Follow Master Lu forever, never quit;
- Attain enlightenment in one lifetime, and transcend the cycle of rebirth for good!

In May 2014, I had the honor of calling Master Lu. He read my totem and enlightened me about the number of Little Houses to recite and fish to release. He told me I was very kind. I was in tears: only the Master could know my heart. The recording was also played at the Hong Kong Dharma Conference in June 2014. I am grateful to Master Lu for His compassion and for giving me the opportunity to propagate the Dharma and conduct merits and virtues using my experience.

After I hung up the phone, I cried and knelt in front of the Buddhist altar to offer the Bodhisattva incense. I made vows to Guan Yin Bodhisattva:

- Release 100,000 fish;
- Offer of 3,000 Dharma Gems to sentient beings free of charge;
- Release 50,000 fish for Master Lu;
- Recite 108 Little Houses per set for 3 sets for Master Lu.

After I made these vows, Bodhisattva blessed me and allowed me to transform with several coworkers and friends because they witnessed me recover in health. Thus, they also want to learn Buddhism and recite Buddhist scriptures.

Over the years, I have repaid my karmic creditors with 3,000 - 4,000 Little Houses, released >40,000 fish, and transformed many sentient beings through my Buddhist experience. Now, I rarely catch a cold throughout the year. More importantly, I have completely recovered from 43 years of asthma! I don't even need a pill. Gratitude for Bodhisattva's mercy, I am now in very good health. People can't tell that I used to be so seriously ill.

Buddhist practitioner: L31

Comments:

- Diligence is one of the Six Paramitas. Only through diligence can one quickly eliminate karma, free oneself from suffering, and attain happiness.
- Good people often suffer, even from a young age, because those who are considered good in this life may not have been good in their past lives. If the karmic obstacles created in a past life were not resolved then, they will inevitably face

retribution in this life.

Case 4: Grateful for Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, my allergic asthma recovered

I am from Ulm, Germany.

I was an allergic asthma patient. My German doctor told me that this disease is chronic and cannot be cured. Every time I have an acute asthma attack, I need an oxygen machine to breathe. When the disease worsens, I need to spray emergency medicine prepared by the doctor for relief. I live in fear and worry every day. In order to get well, I traveled to China twice a year to see Chinese and Western doctors. I then carried a lot of Chinese medicine back to Germany. Like the Taiwan famous singer who died from asthma, a Chinese doctor told me that allergic asthma attacks could be life-threatening anywhere and anytime. The doctor's statement made me fear for my health, and I have lived cautiously ever since, fearing something might happen one day. For this reason, I kept several oxygen machines at home and in the restaurant, taking oxygen in time to save my life in case of an attack.

At the beginning of 2016, I took my mom to Shanghai and I had an attack on the Oriental Pearl Tower. My hands and feet shook, my whole body was weak, and the sudden illness scared me to death. Since I didn't have an oxygen machine with me, the only way was to get away from allergens quickly. However, there were too many people in the 20-story building, so I couldn't leave quickly. All I could do was yell, "Help! Help!" Then I sprayed my first aid all the way down the stairs, pushing my way through the crowds. I sprayed five times. When I got down, I sat on the ground and bawled my eyes out. This horrible experience made me deeply realize how serious my condition is. My illness is exactly like the doctor says, "Life is between breaths. When allergies strike, life can disappear anytime, anywhere." This acute asthma attack happens so often that I thought how fragile and vulnerable my life is.

Grateful for Bodhisattva's compassion and salvation! I met Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door in November 2016. Buddhist practitioner Huang told me that the Four Golden Buddhist Practices of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, "making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, performing life liberation, and reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms*" could save my life. Huang told me about many successful cases after practicing this Dharma Door. It was as if I grasped a lifeline. I realized that my illness was a karmic disease. It was no wonder that no matter how many times I visited the doctor, nothing helped me.

At that time, I immediately invited the Buddhist scriptures of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and Dharma Gems. When I got home, I couldn't wait to recite Buddhist scriptures. I conducted my daily recitation relentlessly. I recited the Little House to my own karmic creditors and to ascend my aborted child. I immediately made a vow to be a vegetarian for the rest of my life. I insisted on going to the river every month to release living creatures. I actively participated in Dharma Conferences and various Buddhist communal study activities.

I remember the first time I traveled to Frankfurt's Guan Yin Citta

Hall. I had an asthma attack and couldn't enter the building to worship the Bodhisattva. A few senior practitioners held me up so I barely could get in. They told me that, with Bodhisattva here, I should not be afraid. I knew the seriousness of my condition and the consequences of an asthma attack were unimaginable. Grateful for the Bodhisattva's compassion and blessings, that day I was actually able to worship the Buddha, recite Buddhist scriptures, and burn Little Houses normally.

In 2017 I had the honor of attending two Dharma Conferences in Milan, Italy and Paris, France. During the Paris Dharma Conference, I had the opportunity to become a disciple of Master Lu and to be one of the hands and eyes of Guan Yin Bodhisattva. When I kneeled in front of Guan Yin Bodhisattva with sincere devotion, Master Lu compassionately empowered me. Master Lu said to me, "Cultivate well," which immediately touched my nature and made me suddenly shed tears from the bottom of my heart, feeling that everything was hard-won. I must cherish it! Shame made me cry my eyes out. After crying, I realized that my chest felt like it had been emptied all of a sudden, a kind of release that I had never experienced before. I knew it was the Bodhisattva who blessed me. A voice in my heart told me I was cured.

After paying homage to Master Lu, I returned to the hotel. I threw away all the first-aid medicine I relied on to save my life in front of many fellow practitioners. One of the practitioners kindly reminded me, saying, "You have to be rational, you are really sick after all." However, my mind strongly told me to believe that Guan Yin Bodhisattva would definitely save me and bless me! If one's thoughts are sincere, the Buddha will respond. Sincerity is the key to success! Guan Yin Bodhisattva is Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate and saves sentient beings from all suffering. The Bodhisattva's compassion and my own persistent belief allowed me to get rid of allergic asthma. My asthma was miraculously cured!

I have noticed a lot of changes in my body after almost three years of eating vegetarian and reciting Buddhist scriptures. I am now healthy and full of energy. My previous low blood pressure, feeling cold and weak, and migraine headaches, which used to be relieved by regular massages, have been cured. As an allergic person, I could become very sick if I didn't pay attention to what I ate. Once I had an attack of gastroenteritis to the point that I entered into shock. Now, through being a vegetarian, my intestines are clean, and the gastrointestinal problems that have been with me all my life have been cured. This event made me very happy. I have also changed my bad nature of complaining all the time, being self-righteous, and being aggressive through studying Buddhism. I have learned to keep the precepts, tolerate others, be compassionate, let go, be grateful, and be more willing to help others.

I sincerely hope everyone can benefit from the Dharma. The Dharma power is boundless, and the benefits are infinite. Please act quickly if you have not yet believed in it. Reciting Buddhist scriptures doesn't cost a penny. Please pick up and recite the Buddhist scriptures to promote family harmony, smart and healthy children, and prevent disasters and diseases from occurring. Practicing Buddhism and reciting Buddhist scriptures

can change a person's destiny, according to my experience.

Buddhist practitioner: L32

Comments:

- Similar to cases 1 and 2, this fellow practitioner also had an abortion. Killing brings too many disasters to humanity; we must not continue to create more killing karma. "Lay down the butcher's knife, and become a Buddha on the spot."
- No matter whether it is a German doctor or a doctor of another nationality, their standard answer on asthma is always the same: this disease is chronic and cannot be cured. This is because doctors cannot detect karma and spirits, and no medicines can remove them.

Case 5: My 50-year asthma was cured in <2 years via Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door

I am a Dharma practitioner from Singapore, now living in Melbourne, Australia. Although I have only been practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door for slightly >1 year, I can't help but share with you my experience of studying Buddhism with great joy in my heart.

There is a Waterloo Street in Singapore. Kwan Im Thong Hood Cho Temple on Waterloo Street is very famous. Everyone who believes in Buddhism knows about it. I often went to the temple to worship the Bodhisattva. At that time, I thought that believing in Buddhism was all about kowtowing and drawing divination sticks. Until one day, I saw people offering Buddhist books for free.

Curious, I walked up and took one. During the conversation, I heard that they often handed out books. Strangely enough, this was the first time I had met them. Predetermined affinity is so marvelous that when it is immature, you can't even see it when it passes by; once it is mature, nothing can stop it.

The book is superb. However, I couldn't help but cringe at the sight of the *Great Compassion Mantra*. Hence, I languished for some time. It was my desire for a faith that finally led me to recite Buddhist scriptures. Being >50 years old, although I often burn incense, Buddhism is still far from being a faith for me. However, one should have faith. This thought became stronger and stronger as I became older. Eventually, I decided to really get into Buddhism and start reciting Buddhist scriptures.

At that time I suffered from insomnia and asthma for many years. Even though I started reciting Buddhist scriptures I never thought it would improve my health. If so, it simply turned my professional thinking as a medical practitioner upside down.

I have had insomnia for many years. At the earliest, I had to work night shifts because of my profession, and I had occasional insomnia. As time passed, insomnia slowly became the norm. After I turned 50, my insomnia got worse and worse, to the extent that I couldn't sleep the whole night. I could count up to 2,000 sheep and still not sleep. By morning I was exhausted and in a trance. I didn't take it seriously when I first experienced insomnia. It was only when it developed into all-night insomnia that I tried all sorts of things but could never solve it. I didn't

even know that reciting Buddhist scriptures could improve sleep quality, so I didn't pray for it. The Bodhisattva really favored me. I didn't expect that after only a week of reciting Buddhist scriptures, I could fall asleep. By now, sleep quality is so much better!

I have had asthma since 2 years old. My mother, who is a pharmacist, filled my prescriptions, took me to the doctor, and did various treatments for my asthma. These measures only provided temporary relief and lengthened the interval between attacks. My mother said my asthma was a sequela of measles, lifelong and impossible to cure. Since asthma has been with me for as long as I can remember, my mother said I would have asthma for life. I have had all kinds of treatments and there is no cure. Therefore, from the deepest part of my heart, I have possessed this kind of stereotypical thinking, and I am also used to it appearing in my life from time to time.

After settling in Singapore, I had to get medicines mailed from China regularly, and I also had to see the doctor on a regular basis. I have seen many doctors. I did not go to the doctor for a cure. It is because, in my mind, my asthma is innate and cannot be cured. Seeing an extra doctor is just a convenience. The doctor prescribed the highest-strength medication. At last, I don't need a prescription from the doctor himself anymore when I shop for medication. I only had to speak to the nurse because everyone knew me too well.

It developed to the point where I couldn't touch anything cold. A mouthful of cold water could trigger a violent cough. I couldn't drink orange juice. I couldn't touch beans. A little bit of air-conditioning would immediately make me cough. Singapore is a tropical country, and in summer, everyone tries to keep themselves cool. However, I have to wear socks at home, and I have to put on a coat when I go out in the car. I am so careful. Sometimes I am fine, but at night, when I lie down, I cough and have to get up and take a spray.

By the time I studied Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, my asthma was very severe. Not only did I have to take strong cough medicine many times a day, but I also had to take hormones to control my condition. Hormone side effects are known to almost everyone, and I knew better as a medical professional, but I simply had no other choice.

Like insomnia, I didn't even think Buddhist scriptures would help my asthma. Once at Singapore Guan Yin Citta Practice Centre (Oriental Radio Practice Centre), while chatting, a Buddhist friend said her asthma had healed after reciting Buddhist scriptures. While others rejoiced over her, I said without thinking, "No way, asthma can't be cured." My words caused the other Buddhists to hastily end the conversation because they were afraid I would continue to create negative verbal karma.

With the deepening of my Buddhism study, I slowly understood the concept of karmic obstacles. I also learned how to recite the *Eighty-eight Buddhas Great Repentance* and Little House to eliminate karmic obstacles. So, on Guan Yin Bodhisattva's birthday in April this year, specifically for my asthma, I recited the *Eighty-eight Buddhas Great Repentance* 27 times and also burned and repaid the Little House to my karmic creditors. However, I still did

not expect immediate results.

Nevertheless, a miracle happened! My husband noticed it first: I stopped coughing! After his reminder, it dawned on me that I hadn't coughed for the past few days. Could it be that the Bodhisattva helped me eliminate my karma? To verify, I drank cold water. Gosh, I didn't cough! I tried eating beans. I was fine! Orange juice, and yogurt, they are all good to go! I went to my best friend's home to report the good news. My friend didn't believe me and tried to turn on the air conditioner to see how I reacted. As a result, the cool air did not bother me! I haven't had an asthma attack once so far. I don't have to be so careful anymore!

The third change in my health achieved by reciting Buddhist scriptures was my back. For years, my back has always felt uncomfortable as if it was pressed against a thick quilt. So, I often went for massages. After reciting Buddhist scriptures, the symptoms also disappeared and my body never felt lighter!

Such a large change in my body was not resolved even after decades of medical treatments. These illnesses were so stubborn that I fully believed they would always be with me. I never thought that reciting Buddhist scriptures for just >1 year would allow me to say goodbye to decades of old ailments. Guan Yin Bodhisattva is so compassionate! The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is excellent! I didn't specifically pray for the Bodhisattva to help me treat my illnesses, but the fact that it happened makes me believe in Master Lu's teaching: "Miracles will happen!"

Buddhist practitioner: N33

Comments:

- The mother is a pharmacist and the fellow practitioner is a medical professional. They are helpless in the face of asthma. This is very sad and also highlights the fact that humanity's understanding of nature is still very limited.
- This practitioner's mind is filled with worldly medical knowledge. She is too attached to her own inherent beliefs to accept that asthma can be cured. Master Lu has taught that the most important aspect of cultivating the mind is to eliminate internal attachments.

Discussion

Like thousands of other rare and intractable diseases, scientists cannot identify the cause of asthma [17]. However, Master Lu, by examining patients' totems in heaven, identified the true cause of their asthma. In Q&A 2, the patient has many spirits in her throat area. In Q&A 3, the patient's ailment is attributed to three spirits: one human and two animal spirits. Upon careful review of the conversation between Master Lu and the patient, particularly regarding the patient's third uncle, the listener precisely validated Master Lu's findings.

According to Master Lu's theory, patients will recover their health by ascending spirits from their bodies. The successful restoration of health in the 5 Dharma practitioners (Case 1-5) under Master Lu's guidance serves as evidence supporting the authenticity of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. Furthermore, it challenges the previous belief that asthma cannot be cured.

In today's world, various strange diseases are becoming increasingly common. Despite the diverse causes, killing karma is one of the most significant factors behind these illnesses, and asthma is no exception. Cases 1, 2, and 4 all involve abortion, and Case 1 also includes the karma of killing animals. While these actions may not break human laws, they do violate the laws of the underworld. According to the law of cause and effect, these actions will inevitably lead to karmic retribution. Asthma in these three individuals is the retribution caused by the manifestation of killing karma. In Case 1, the cause-and-effect relationship is particularly clear: her severe asthma began in the winter of the year she had the abortion.

In addition to killing karma, speech karma is also a cause of asthma. In a past life, if one's speech was not in accordance with Dharma and in accordance with the principles, it could lead to asthma in this life, making it difficult for the person to speak or express clearly [18]. The mouth is the root of trouble. As an old Chinese saying goes, "Trouble comes from the mouth, and illness enters through the mouth." It is important to manage one's speech carefully, as careless words can even lead to fatal consequences. A single statement can either bring ruin to a nation or revive it [19].

In Case 5, the practitioner's pharmacist mother attributed the practitioner's asthma to "a sequela of measles, lifelong and impossible to cure." While the description "lifelong and impossible to cure" aligns with the medical perspective, Master Lu's teachings challenge the assertion that it is solely "a sequela of measles." According to Master Lu, measles acts as a triggering factor, causing karma to flare up and result in spirits occupying the body, leading to asthma. If the fellow practitioner contracted a cold at age 2, she might also have developed asthma. Even if she had not contracted measles at age 2, a similar manifestation of asthma could have occurred later in life, perhaps during a predestined 369 calamity [17]. Thus, the fundamental cause is not the trigger factor but the karma in her body.

For a child (Case 3) and a 2-year-old baby (Case 5), they might have no time to create lots of negative karma in this life. Where did their karma come from? Their karma can originate from 2 main sources. Firstly, it was generated during their previous lives and was carried over to these lives. Secondly, it can be 'inherited' from their ancestors. This includes the potential influence of their mother's actions during pregnancy, such as consuming live animals or generating excessive karma related to the respiratory system, or the baby's birthday party involving lots of animal killing, etc. This holistic view integrates the Dharma idea that karma is a complex web of interconnected influences that transcend individual lifetimes.

Karma from a previous life manifesting in this one can be seen in the case of a psoriasis patient who harmed a man by causing his skin to be severely burned in a previous life [17], and a 5-year-old cancer patient who killed two cows in a previous life [20]. Karma created by ancestors can also affect their descendants, leading to karmic retribution. For instance, we have previously discussed the case of an autistic boy [17]. Another vivid example is presented in Q&A 3 of this paper, where the listener's father raised chickens and killed other large animals, creating significant

killing karma. When this karma was retributed, it resulted in the son becoming ill.

People who have not encountered Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door may not understand why his third uncle's soul (spirit) entered his body and made him sick, especially since his uncle loved him very much when he was alive (Q&A 3). This is difficult to understand from a human perspective. However, from the perspective of Dharma, it is very easy to comprehend.

There is no love without reason and no hate without cause. This statement holds true from a Dharma perspective. His third uncle's fondness for him since childhood was due to a karmic connection from a previous life. Their karmic bond was so deep that it extended into this life, bringing them into the same family. With karmic ties come debts, and with debts come repayment. Thus, after his uncle died, his soul entered the boy's body because of the uncle's strong love for him. In fact, if you have watched Master Lu's Totem reading programs, you will find that a large proportion of the spirits in patient's bodies come from deceased relatives, referred to in Buddhism as karmic creditors.

Once attached to the body, spirits can adversely affect patients in various ways. For instance, Master Lu identified a cat spirit scratching a patient's stomach, causing her stomach problems, which correlated with her history of raising a cat. Another Dharma practitioner experienced digestive issues and bloating, with Master Lu identifying a spirit turtle covering her stomach. Sleep paralysis and mental disorders are attributed to spirits controlling the body and brain, respectively. Spirits can deliver 'electric shocks' to people, as documented in patient P18 of a previous observation [17]. Despite lacking physical forms, spirits can wield power that causes harm. When spirits engage in actions like scratching or manipulating, corresponding organ issues, such as asthma, may manifest. Once asthma develops, the patients will carry it for the rest of their lives.

Insights from the provided examples suggest a connection between spirits and respiratory system afflictions. Asthma is posited to result from spirits residing in the respiratory system, causing damage to the lungs and bronchi (Q&A 2-3). Clinical manifestations include chronic inflammation and respiratory tract remodeling [21], elevated matrix metalloproteinase-2, IL-6, and IgE serum levels [22], and heightened sensitivity to pollen [23], among others. Conventional medical approaches often target symptoms, such as using anti-immunoglobulin E, anti-interleukin-5/interleukin-5R, anti-interleukin-4/interleukin-13R, and anti-thymic stromal lymphopoietin medications [24]. These treatments can reduce exacerbations and improve asthma control, but they cannot eradicate the illness. Addressing the root cause, which involves spirits affecting the respiratory system, remains a challenge for science. The inability to diagnose these spiritual influences contributes to the persistent challenge of resolving asthma, as reflected in statements like "there is no cure for asthma" from doctors and health agencies.

Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door treats asthma by removing its root cause: eliminating karma and ascending spirits. When karma and spirits in the respiratory area are removed, the patient is naturally healed. Thus, to recover from asthma, one must accept

the concept of Dharma. For those unwilling to embrace Dharma, the Bodhisattva's limitless power cannot intervene due to the karmic law.

Both karma and spirits may cause other diseases besides asthma. When one removes karma and ascends the spirits, other diseases will also heal, too. This, in turn, proves that these diseases are caused by karmic obstacles or spirit-related issues. For example, in Case 1, her heart disease, lumbar spine disease, cervical spondylosis, muscle aches, and limb stiffness all disappeared after practicing Buddhism. In Case 3, she rarely catches a cold afterward. In Case 4, her previous low blood pressure, feeling of cold and weakness, migraine headaches and chronic gastroenteritis have all been cured. In Case 5, her long-term insomnia and chronic back discomfort were resolved. She is no longer afraid of cold water, beans, orange juice, yogurt, or air conditioner cold air.

Furthermore, the fact that they are no longer sensitive to foods (Case 4-5) and temperature change (Case 5) indicates that allergens and environmental factors are not the root causes of asthma, but merely trigger flare-ups when karma and spirits are present. Without karma and spirits, these factors lose their triggering effect.

From our previous report and the current study, we have demonstrated that the key to treating rare and intractable diseases is eliminating karma. People may wonder whether there is a more effective way to remove karma to speed up the healing process. In fact, there are significant dates that can help us to remove karma quickly. These dates include the first and fifteenth of each lunar month, the Lunar New Year, the Solar New Year, the birthdays of Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, their enlightenment days, ordination days, and so on. On these auspicious days, the Buddhas and Bodhisattvas descend to the human realm more frequently, allowing for faster elimination of karma if we seriously repent.

For instance, a lung cancer patient, L24, recited the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* 87 times on New Year's Eve, despite experiencing extreme weakness and pain. The next day, her health condition significantly improved [20]. Similarly, N33 (Case 5), recited the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* 27 times on Guan Yin Bodhisattva's birthday, specifically for her asthma, and also repaid some Little Houses to her karmic creditors. Her asthma, which had troubled her for 50 years, was healed. These examples suggest that repenting on auspicious days can lead to immediate karma elimination.

Na Mo Zhan Tan Gong De Fo (or Chandan Merit Buddha or Buddha of Sandalwood Merit) gave guidance to a fellow practitioner [25]: "As an ancient Buddha enshrined in the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, I advise everyone to engage in repentance frequently. The *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* must be recited sincerely. It is truly extraordinary; the most important aspect of practicing Buddhism and reciting scriptures is repentance, which is an indispensable step." "Regarding reciting the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* on the birthdays of Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, many people do not understand and think, 'Isn't reciting Little Houses the same for eliminating karma?'

The birthdays of Buddhas and Bodhisattvas are auspicious days added to the calendar, and you must seize these good days to repent. Repent for the wrongdoings of this life, do not repeat them, and correct yourself. On that day, a lot of karma will be eliminated, so seize the opportunity and do not miss it. Listening to Master Lu's teachings is very meaningful for you."

In contrast to the significant days, which can bring good fortune, the holidays of the underworld can bring depression, pain, and even illness. These holidays include Qingming Festival, Ghost Festival, and Winter Solstice. Master Lu has explained that during these holidays, spirits are released from the underworld a month in advance. After being released, they return to their previous home to cause trouble [26]. For example, S22's grandfather developed Alzheimer's disease before the Ghost Festival [27]. When creditors come to collect debts, we have no choice but to repay them, which is a natural law. One can either repay the debts by reciting Buddhist scriptures or by enduring physical suffering. Whether to repay through scripture recitation or physical suffering is up to the individual. In any case, one must be prepared to repay debts around the underworld holidays.

Apparently, repaying debts through Little Houses is a wiser choice than through physical suffering. In fact, learning Buddhism is about gaining wisdom. Another important aspect of learning Buddhism is to cultivate compassion. When pitiful spirits come to you seeking ascension, offering them Little Houses to help them elevate to a higher realm is an act of great compassion.

Without practicing Buddhism, one is helplessly driven by karma through the six realms of reincarnation. In this life, they may suffer from asthma; in the next life, they do not know into which realm they will be reborn, nor what illness or difficulty they might face.

Given the success of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door in treating asthma and the limitations of conventional medicine in addressing this condition, along with the multiple successes in treating many other medically incurable diseases [17, 20, 27], we believe it is time to promote this Dharma Door to all humanity. Just as the fruits of centuries of medical advancements in science are disseminated worldwide and benefit numerous patients, Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door should also be made accessible to all, allowing everyone to benefit.

It is regrettable for someone not to understand science, but it is even more regrettable not to understand Dharma. Without this understanding, one cannot escape from karmic repercussions. Asthma serves as a poignant example of this truth.

Recovery

We must understand that diseases that doctors cannot treat are often karmic in nature, stemming from wrongdoings we committed in our current and/or previous lives. To heal, we must repent for our past misdeeds. Without this repentance, we cannot eliminate our karma, and without removing karma, we cannot heal. Asthma is such a disease, serving as a punishment for our past wrongdoings.

Once diagnosed with asthma, the disease is typically considered a lifelong condition given the current state of medical knowledge.

However, within the Dharma, there is a way. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door offers the 5 Golden Buddhist Practices to treat asthma by eliminating karma and ascending spirits. Specifically, you can refer to the five cases in this paper for guidance on:

- Making vows;
- Reciting Buddhist scriptures;
- Performing life liberation;
- Reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms*;
- Repent of wrongdoings and refrain from doing them.

The principles explaining why these Dharma practices can help heal diseases are addressed previously [17, 28, 29].

The time required for recovery will vary from person to person because the karma burden differs. For example, the karma for killing humans and animals is different, and the karma for aborting a baby who is a karmic creditor differs from that of aborting a baby who is a karmic debtor. The power of one's vows also plays a role; stronger vows can lead to faster karma elimination. Additionally, releasing animals yourself is different from asking others to do it on your behalf, and sincerity matters significantly. As Master Lu enlightened in Q&A 1, one should keep practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door until the asthma is gone.

Prevention

The phenomenon of asthma manifesting at various ages, particularly adult-onset or late-onset asthma, has long perplexed the scientific community. From a Dharma perspective, this can be explained through the concept of karmic obstacles. If these karmic obstacles in the respiratory organs and tissues manifest at ages 2, 3, or 45, asthma will appear at those respective ages 2 (Case 5), 3 (Q&A 3), and 45 (Case 2). Since respiratory karmic obstacles can manifest at any age, asthma can similarly occur at any age. Therefore, from this viewpoint, preventing the manifestation of karmic obstacles is crucial to preventing the development of asthma.

However, the concept of asthma prevention via Dharma differs completely from asthma prevention via medicine, such as using probiotics in asthma prevention [30]. Dharma-based prevention aims to prevent karmic obstacles from manifesting as asthma, while medical prevention focuses on preventing asthma exacerbations and worsening symptoms. A single instance of a karmic flare-up can result in the onset of asthma, making it a lifelong condition. In contrast, asthma exacerbations can occur multiple times throughout a person's life. Karmic flare-ups generally occur during specific predestined ages, such as 369 [17], whereas asthma exacerbations are triggered by specific factors like allergens, which can happen at any time (Case 4 and 5).

From the Dharma perspective, when a karmic flare-up results in asthma, the spirits occupy the respiratory system, causing sensitivities to triggers such as pollen and temperature changes. An asthma exacerbation leads to airway narrowing, resulting in breathing difficulties and potential suffocation. Therefore, preventing karmic flare-ups is more crucial than merely

preventing asthma exacerbations.

Shakyamuni Buddha taught Dharma for 49 years, often by answering questions posed by His disciples. Similarly, Master Lu spreads the teachings of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door through His book, *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, Dharma talks at conferences, and by answering fellow practitioners' questions via phone calls and live events. Since no practitioner has specifically asked about methods to prevent asthma, there isn't a dedicated answer from Master Lu on this topic. However, based on Master Lu's past teachings and presentations by fellow practitioners, we can summarize the main factors and take preventive measures by avoiding the known causes of asthma.

First, refrain from killing, which includes avoiding abortions and not eating live sea or freshwater animals. Avoiding killing not only prevents you from acquiring asthma but also prevents your offspring from acquiring it.

Second, guard against committing karma of speech [31]. The Buddha once warned His disciples: "You should guard against committing karma of speech, for the consequences of evil speech are more dreadful than a raging fire." Evil speech can lead to mouth ulcers, stuttering, severe illnesses, terminal diseases, loneliness, and the loss of all merits and virtues. Certainly, the karma of evil speech can also lead to asthma [18].

For healthy individuals, don't take these matters lightly. If you have committed acts of killing or harmful speech, repent immediately. Use the Five Golden Buddhist Practices of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door to eliminate karmic obstacles [17]. This is the wisest method to prevent asthma.

Conclusion

Asthma is caused by karma located in the respiratory area, with spirit manifestations in this region. Therefore, it is considered a karmic or spiritual disease. Practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door can effectively treat asthma.

Triggering factors are not the cause of asthma. Their triggering effects depend on whether one possesses karma or spirits.

To prevent asthma, abstain from committing killing karma and evil karma of speech.

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Ethical Statement

The author did not involve any part of the experimental design, experimental treatments and result analysis of the 5 Dharma practitioners. All the experimental procedures and practices by the 5 presenters were done by themselves independently.

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Statement by Translator and Writer

The 5 stories in the text, were translated from Chinese to English based on their intended meaning rather than a word-for-word approach. The remaining portions of the paper were written based on my limited understanding of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. If there are any inaccuracies or deviations from the true meaning of the Chinese version, or if the content does not accurately reflect Master Lu's teachings, I sincerely seek forgiveness from the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, Dharma Protectors, and Master Jun Hong Lu.

Disclaimer of Liability

The contents of the presentation, comments, discussion, recovery, prevention and conclusion including text, images, and other information obtained from Dharma practitioners, are provided strictly for reference purposes. Due to the unique nature of individual karma, results similar to those experienced by the practitioners may not be replicated. The experiences and advice shared should not be construed as medical advice or a diagnosis.

In the event of an emergency, it is crucial to promptly contact your doctor or emergency services by dialing 911. Relying on any information found in this paper is done solely at your own risk. The author bears no responsibility for the consequences. By using or misusing the contents, you accept liability for any personal injury, including death. It is imperative to exercise caution and seek professional medical guidance for health-related concerns.

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